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Both expanded and uncultured mesenchymal stem cells from MDS patients are genomically abnormal, showing a specific genetic profile for the 5q- syndrome

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The presence of cytogenetic aberrations on mesenchymal stem cells (MSC) from myelodysplastic syndrome (MDS) patients is controversial. The aim of the study is to characterize bone marrow (BM) derived MSC from patients with MDS using kinetic studies, immunophenotyping, fluorescent in situ hybridization (FISH) and genetic changes by array-based comparative genomic hybridization (array-CGH). In all 36 cases of untreated MDS were studied. MDS–MSC achieved confluence at a significantly slower rate than donor-MSC, and the antigenic expression of CD105 and CD104 was lower. Array-CGH studies showed DNA genomic changes that were proven not to be somatic. These results were confirmed by FISH. To confirm that genomic changes were also present in freshly obtained MSCs they were enriched by sorting BM cells with the following phenotype: CD45 - /CD73 ++ /CD34 - /CD271 ++. They also showed genomic changes that were confirmed by FISH. To analyze the relationship of these aberrations with clinical-biological data an unsupervised hierarchical cluster analysis was performed, two clusters were identified: the first one included the 5q- syndrome patients, whereas the other incorporated other MDS. Our results show, for the first time that MSC from MDS display genomic aberrations, assessed by array-CGH and FISH, some of them specially linked to a particular MDS subtype, the 5q- syndrome.

Introduction

Myelodysplastic syndrome (MDS) are a group of clonal disorders of pluripotent hematopoietic stem cells, characterized by ineffective hematopoiesis and a heightened potential to evolve into acute myelocytic leukemia.¹ MDS is the result of a multi-step sequence of genomic injuries to Bone Marrow (BM) stem cell. Although clonal chromosomal abnormalities are detected in 40–70% of de novo MDS, and in 95% of therapy-related MDS, there is no cytogenetic abnormality specific for MDS.² In the pathophysiology of MDS not only cytogenetic and molecular abnormalities are implicated but also some other factors such as DNA hypermethylation, immune dysregulation and an increased frequency of apoptosis in the BM cells.³

The hematopoietic microenvironment plays a role in the physiology of hematopoiesis, controlling the formation of blood cells through the production and secretion of cytokines and extracellular matrix molecules. Mesenchymal stem cells (MSC) are key components of the hematopoietic microenvironment and the research on their implication in several diseases is expanding. Microenvironment is involved in the pathophysiology of MDS,⁴ and the abnormal production of certain cytokines by BM-derived fibroblasts of MDS is nowadays accepted.^{5,6}

Nevertheless, the question of whether MSC from MDS patients are abnormal is not clear. Although some groups have reported that MSC display both a normal growth pattern and a normal surface antigen expression as compared with MSC from healthy individuals,^{7–9} other authors have shown discrepant results.^{4,8,10} Even more confusion exists regarding whether or not MSC from MDS display cytogenetic abnormalities. The studies in this field are scanty and again they show discrepant results from absence of chromosomal markers,^{7,11} to the presence of karyotypic aberrations such as hypodiploid cells.^{4,8,10}

This study aimed to analyze the characteristics of MSC from MDS patients including the growth pattern, the immunophenotype and their cytogenetic characterization by array-based comparative genomic hybridization (array-CGH).

Materials and methods

Patient characteristics

36 BM cells from 'de novo' MDS, corresponding to 33 patients, were included in the study. Male/female ratio was 17/16 and median age was 70 years (range, 34–89 years). MDS diagnosis was established by peripheral blood counts and morphology, BM morphology and cytogenetic analyses and classified according to the WHO proposals.¹² Patients' characteristics are summarized in Table 1. Three cases not previously treated were also analyzed at progression (cases 16, 18 and 20). None of them had received treatment during this period of time, other than supportive therapy. Normal BM samples were obtained from 15 healthy donors, eight men and seven women, with a median age of 57 years (range, 37–88 years). Written informed consent was obtained from all patients and donors according to the ethical guidelines of our institution.

Isolation and expansion of MSC

Mononuclear cells from BM were isolated by centrifugation (1200 r.p.m. for 30 min) using Ficoll-Paque Plus (Amersham Biosciences AB, Uppsala, Sweden) density gradient.¹³ Mononuclear cells were plated at a concentration of 1×10^6 cells/cm² and cultured in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (Gibco, BRL, Invitrogen Corporation, Paisley, UK) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS; BioWhittaker, Lonza, Veviers, Belgium) and 1% antibiotics (Penicillin–Streptomycin, Gibco, Invitrogen Corporation). Every 5 days non-adherent cells were removed and the medium was changed. When the cultures reached 80% confluence, they were trypsinized (0.05% Trypsin-EDTA; Gibco, Invitrogen Corporation),¹⁴ and further expanded. Cultures were incubated at 37 °C in an atmosphere of 5% CO₂ air.

Morphological analysis and cell surface antigen analysis

The morphology of the cells was examined every 5 days under a phase-contrast microscope. MSC were characterized according to the International Society of Cell Therapy consensus antibody panel.¹⁵ The monoclonal antibodies used were: anti-CD34-APC, -CD19-APC, -CD45-PerCPCy5.5, -HLA-DR-PerCPCy5.5, -CD14-FITC, -CD56-PE, -CD62L-PE, -CD49A-PE, -CD117-PE (Becton Dickinson Biosciences, San Jose, CA, USA), anti-CD90-FITC, -CD73-PE, -CD166-PE, -CD106-PE, -CD104-PE, -CD49B-FITC (BD Biosciences Pharmingen, San Jose, CA, USA), anti-CD54-FITC (Serotec, Oxford, UK), anti-CD133-PE (Miltenyi Biotec, Bergisch Gladbach, Germany), anti-CD105-FITC (ImmunoStep, Salamanca, Spain). The analysis of the cell surface molecules was performed at the same passage as the cytogenetic analyses, using part of the cells for the flow cytometry analysis and part for the cytogenetic analysis. Harvested cells were washed with PBS (BD FACSCFlow, BD Biosciences, San Jose, CA, USA), 2.5×10^5 cells were suspended in PBS and incubated with combinations of the monoclonal antibodies listed above, at dilutions recommended by the manufacturers. Their corresponding isotype control was also included. The labelled cells were acquired on a FACSCalibur flow cytometer (Becton Dickinson Biosciences, San Jose, CA, USA) using the CellQuest program (Becton Dickinson Biosciences), by collecting 50 000 cells, and further analyzed using the Paint-A-Gate program (Becton Dickinson Biosciences).¹⁶

To compare the expression level of each antigen the mean channel fluorescence intensity was related with the isotopic control before comparing with the rest of the cells.

Differentiation assays

To fulfil the International Society for Cellular Therapy requirements for MSC definition, adipogenic, osteogenic and chondrogenic differentiation was performed. To induce osteoblastic and adipocytic differentiation, MSC from cases number 8, 10, 14, 16 and 31 were harvested and plated at 4th passage on a chamber slide system (SlideFlask, Nunc, Roskilde, Denmark). When the cells had reached a confluence of above 80%, the medium was changed to the specific differentiation medium that was changed every 3–4 days during the 14 days. The osteoblastic differentiation medium was composed of DMEM, 10% FBS, 1% antibiotics and 10mM of β -glycerophosphate (Sigma-Aldrich Inc., Milwaukee, WI, USA). The adipocytic medium was composed of Iscove's modified Dulbecco's Medium (Gibco, Paisley, UK), 10% FBS, 1% antibiotics, 10% horse serum and 5×10^{-7} hydrocortisone (Sigma-Aldrich Co). To evaluate the osteoblastic differentiation, the cells were stained with alkaline phosphatase using a commercial kit (Super-Sensitive/HC Detection Systems, BioGenex, Duiven, The Netherlands). The staining with Oil-red-O (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany) was used in the adipocytic differentiation.¹⁴ For chondrocytic differentiation, MSC from case numbers 8, 10 and 14 were harvested at 3rd passage, and 1×10^6 cells were centrifuged for 10 min at 1200 r.p.m., in a 15ml conical polypropylene tube. The pellet was cultured with 0.5 ml of the commercial

differentiation medium (ChondroDiff, Miltenyi Biotec, Bergisch Gladbach, Germany). The medium was changed every 4 days until day 21. This pelleted micromass¹⁷ was stained with Masson Trichrome and immunohistochemical staining for collagen type II.

DNA analysis

To analyze the percentage of MSC that were at different stages of cell cycle a DNA analysis was performed. MSC from cases 8, 9, 10, 13 and 14 were harvested at 3rd passage, and the pellet was washed with PBS. Cells were incubated at room temperature with ribonuclease (40 U/ml) (Sigma Diagnostics Inc.) for 10 min, and later with 1 mg/ml propidium iodide (Sigma Diagnostics) for 15 min also at room temperature. The PI fluorescence was measured using the FACSCalibur flow cytometer, and the analysis was performed with the Paint-A-Gate software.¹⁸

Apoptosis assays

MSC from MDS, case numbers 8, 9, 10, 13 and 14, were analyzed on 3rd passage performing an apoptosis assay, using the Annexin V-PE and 7-ActinomycinD-PerCPCy5.5, kit (BD Pharmingen, BD Biosciences Pharmingen, San Diego, CA, USA), following manufacturer's instructions.¹⁹

Isolation of MSCs

Isolation of MSCs directly from BM was performed, in cases 33, 34, 35 and 36, using a FACS Aria flow cytometer (Becton Dickinson Biosciences-BDB-, San Jose, CA, USA), equipped with the FACSDiva software (BDB). Prior to sorting, cells were stained with a single four-color combination of monoclonal antibodies (MAb): anti-CD45-FITC (Miltenyi Biotec) /anti-CD73-PE (BD Biosciences Pharmingen, San Jose, CA, USA) /anti-CD34-PeCy5 (Immunotech Coulter Company, Marseille, France) /anti-CD271-APC (Miltenyi Biotec), according to well established stain-and-then-lyse-and-wash procedures which have been described earlier.²⁰ The strategy used for the identification of MSC (CD45-/CD73+/CD34-/CD271+),²¹ is illustrated in Figure 1a. Owing to the low proportion of MSC in the sample, acquisition was performed in two consecutive steps to increase the sensitivity of the analysis. First, a total of 50 000 events corresponding to the total nucleated cells present in the sample were acquired. In a second step, acquisition through a 'live gate' drawn on the CD73+/CD271+ region in which MSCs are located was performed (Figure 1b). The purity of the isolated cell populations was evaluated after acquiring 3x10⁶ cells corresponding to the FACS-sorted cell fraction (FACS Aria flow cytometer) and it was 499% (Figure 1c).²⁰

Array-CGH and FISH analysis of MSC

Array-CGH analysis of cultured MSC. Genome-wide analysis of DNA copy number changes of MSC from 13 cases was performed using array-CGH. Slides containing 3032 bacterial artificial chromosomes (BACs) were produced in Centro de Investigación del Cáncer (Salamanca, Spain). The particular BAC and P-1-derived artificial chromosome set used to produce this array is distributed to academic institutions by the Wellcome Trust Sanger Institute (Cambridge, UK) and contains targets spaced at E1Mb density over full genome, a set of subtelomeric sequences for each chromosome arm and a few hundred probes selected for their involvement in oncogenesis. The clone content is available in the 'Cytoview' Windows of the Sanger Institute mapping database site, Ensembl (<http://www.ensembl.org/>). According to this database, clones were ordered along the chromosomes. These clones were isolated from their bacterial cultures with the relevant antibiotics and the DNA was extracted with the standard protocol of Wellcome Trust Sanger Institute. Here, 10 ng of DNA (BAC/PAC) was used as a template for three DOP-PC.^{22,23} These products were ethanol precipitated and dissolved in distilled water. A minimum of three replicates per clone were printed by Microgrid II (Biorobotics, Ann Harbor, MI, USA) on each slide (Ultragaps Coated Slides, Corning, NY, USA) using the aqueous dimethylsulfoxide buffer as spotting solution. Briefly, for labelling reactions, 1 mg of nonamplified genomic DNA, test and reference were digested separately with DpnII restriction enzyme (New England Biolabs, Beverly, MA, USA). For microarray hybridization, the digested DNAs were separately labelled using random primers (Bioprimer labelling kit, Invitrogen, Paisley, UK) and cyanine dye-3-dCTP and cyanine dye-5-dCTP fluorescent dye to paired hybridization simples (Amersham Biosciences, Uppsala, Sweden). The incorporation of the label nucleotide was quantified using the Nanodrop spectrophotometer. Labelled test and reference DNAs were mixed equitably, co-precipitated in the presence of Cot-1 human DNA (Roche, Indianapolis, IN, USA) with ethanol, washed and resuspended in hybridization solution (50% Formamide, 10% Dextran sulfate, 2_ standard saline citrate, 10mM Tris pH 7.6, 2.7% sodium dodecyl sulfate and 10 mg/ml of yeast tRNA). DNA mixtures were hybridized to the arrays in the TECAN HS4800 Pro

according to the manufacturer's recommended protocol. Images and signal intensities were acquired using GenePix4000B (Axon Instruments, Burlingame, CA, USA) dual laser scanner in combination with GenePixPro4.0 (Axon Instruments) imaging software.

Image and data analysis. Spot intensities measured by the GenePix Pro 4.1 software (Axon Instruments, Wetsbur BV, Leuden, The Netherland). Pixel intensities for each feature were integrated and median values were determined, and the local background was calculated. For each spot the intensities were corrected by subtracting the local background for both wavelengths, and only spots with signal intensities at least threefold above background signal intensities were included in the analysis. The median of the ratios of all spots was calculated and used to normalize all data points. From each feature, the log₂ value of the average of the normalization ratios of the spots was calculated and used to display the data. In addition, fluorescence ratios were normalized for each microarray using the print-tip loess method and the background subtraction with the Diagnosis and Normalization Arrays Data tool.²⁴ The cutoff level was determined for each individual experiment after averaging the ratios from the two color-switch hybridizations and subsequent for normalization, and calculate the mean and s.d. to define the cutoff level as means plus/minus two times the s.d. The clones that showed possible changes were submitted to the database of genomics variants (<http://projects.tcag.ca/variation/>) and chromosomal imbalances and phenotype in humans using Ensembl Resources (DECIPHER: <http://www.sanger.ac.uk/PostGenomics/decipher/>).

Clustering

Unsupervised clustering. We converted the relative ratio value for each BAC clones in each sample to score of 1 (gain/amplified), 0 (no change), or -1 (loss) based on the 2 s.d. standards described above and analyzed with Cluster and TreeView²⁵ (Cluster and TreeView software) based on the average linkage method with the centered correlation metric was used (or Pearson Uncentered).

Supervised. Sam analysis was used (<http://www-stat.stanford.edu/~tibs/SAM>)²⁶ to identify BACs that segregate subgroups on MSC. BACs with an s.d. of zero across the data set before analysis were removed. The array data has been deposited in the gene expression omnibus database, the accession number is GSE10822.

Array-CGH on sorted-uncultured MSC. After the sorting, Genomic DNA was extracted using a standard proteinase K digestion followed by phenol/chloroform extraction and resuspended in TE buffer pH 7.5. The concentration of the samples was measured by spectrophotometer (Nanodrop ND-100 spectrophotometer; Nanodrop Technologies, Roeland, DE, USA).

GenomiPhi DNA amplification kit was used following the manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, 1 ml of template was mixed with 9 ml of sample buffer. The mixture was denatured at 95 °C for 3 min and immediately cooled at 4 °C for a minimum of 10 min a combinational of 9 ml of reaction buffer with 1 ml of the enzyme was added to the cooled sample and then incubated at 30 °C for 16 h overnight. Inactivation of the enzyme was performed by heating the sample for 10 min at 65°C, which was the cooled to 4 °C. The postamplification cleanup was achieved by ethanol precipitation using the sodiumacetate/EDTA. Given that negative controls of Phi29 amplified reactions also show a smear in agarose gel, we determined whether the amplified products contained actual genomics by performing a PCR, using specific primers.

Array-CGH was carried out as described in the previous paragraphs with minor modifications. For obtaining optimal results in experiments, both test and reference DNA were amplified using the same amount of starting DNA.

FISH analysis of MSC. To confirm array-CGH results fluorescent in situ hybridization (FISH) analysis were performed with the probe obtained from the BAC RPC11-440G22 (1q31.12), and BAC RP11-132L11 (7p13). DNA probes were labeled either with biotin-11-dUTP or with digoxigenin-11-d-UTP by a standard nick translation reaction. The hybridization was performed according to previously reported procedures.²⁷ Briefly, probes were denatured and preannealed with Cot-1 DNA and hybridized overnight on pretreated denatured chromosome spreads. After washing, the biotin-labeled probes were detected with two layers of avidin-FITC.

Array-CGH of hematopoietic cells

Mononuclear cells from peripheral blood of three cases, numbers 21, 22 and 24, were isolated at diagnosis and used as controls to be sure that changes were not somatic changes. DNA from these cells was isolated and the array performed as described for MSC.

Array-CGH of T lymphocytes from peripheral blood

T lymphocytes of case numbers 33, 34, 35 and 36 were obtained from peripheral blood; after separating mononuclear cells by density gradient, the T lymphocyte population was selected by CD3 using the immunomagnetic protocol for AutoMACS (CD3 microbeads human, MACS Miltenyi Biotec). DNA from these cells was isolated and the array was performed as described for MSC.14,28

Statistics

The SPSS version 15.0 software (Chicago, IL, USA) was used for statistical analysis. The central tendency of data was measured by the median and the dispersion of values around the median was expressed as the range. Statistical analysis was performed by using the Student's t-test. Values of $P < 0.05$ were considered significant.

Results

MSC cultures

MSC confluent layers were obtained in all healthy donors, with a median number of five passages (range, 2–7), and time to reach confluence of 15.5 days (11.6–30). However, when expansion of MSC from MDS patients was assessed, more time ($P < 0.05$) was needed until confluence was achieved, 23.5 days (12–90) (Supplementary Figure 1) and only able to survive the third passage (range, 0–5). Moreover in six MDS cases, cells did not reach confluence and they could not be expanded (Cases 11, 20, 26, 27, 29 and 30).

Also MSC layers morphology was different in donors and patients. Cells from donors showed the characteristic fibroblastlike aspect, but MSC from MDS seemed to be more 'thick and granular' (Figure 2).

Phenotypic analysis of MSC

It should be pointed out that the purity of MSC was above 98% in all cases (Supplementary Figure 2). Cells from cultures were consistently devoid of hematopoietic cells (HC) being negative for hematopoietic antigens CD45, CD34, CD14, CD19 and HLA-DR and were positive for the following antigens CD73, CD90, CD166, CD105, CD104, CD106. When the fluorescence intensity of surface antigens of MSC of MDS was compared with those of MSC from 15 healthy donors, a lower expression of CD105 and CD104 was observed (Supplementary Figure 3 $P < 0.05$). All other antigens analyzed showed a similar expression pattern.

Differentiation assays

To further characterize MSC from MDS, differentiation assays recommended by The International Society for Cellular Therapy were performed. 15 Adipocytic and osteoblastic differentiation assays were performed in five cases, (8, 10, 14, 16 and 31). Chondrocytic differentiation was performed in three cases (8, 10 and 14). Osteoblastic and Adipocytic differentiation was achieved with a similar efficiency than those of normal MSC. However, when chondrocytic differentiation was analyzed we could observe an impaired capacity of cells from MDS to differentiate to chondrocyte lineage as the disposition of collagen II-positive cells in MDS cases is different from those observed in healthy donors (Supplementary Figure 4).

DNA analysis and apoptosis studies

To know why cell expansion was impaired in MSC from MDS patients, cell cycle analysis was performed in five cases (8, 9, 10, 13 and 14) and compared to cell cycle of eight donors. Most MSC from MDS patients were at the G0-G1 phase (median 96.54% (95.5–97.6%)) with a very low percentage of cells in S phase (median 0.63% (0.2–0.6%)). No significant differences between MSC from MDS and donors were observed. The proportion of apoptotic MSC was also analyzed in this five cases, and although it was slightly higher in MDS patients (23.3 vs 20.6). The difference did not reach statistical difference.

Array-CGH analysis of MSC

Array-CGH arrays were performed in 17 cases. 13 MDS cases were analyzed by array-CGH after MSCs expansion : (Cases 1, 8, 10, 12, 16, 17, 18, 21, 22, 24, 26, 27 and 30). In other four cases (33, 34, 35 and 36) array-CGH were performed in parallel, after MSCs sorting and in after 2nd passage expanded MSCs. All the cases included in the array-CGH analysis showed some alterations, with gains more frequent than losses. None of the clones showing modifications have been described to be associated with polymorphic variations except RP11-153P4 located on 9q34.2. Even more, in the three cases in whom array-CGH were performed in HC from peripheral blood and in expanded MSC, the abnormalities found in MSC were not present in HC. Furthermore, array-CGH were performed in T lymphocytes from four patients and those cells did not have the cytogenetic abnormalities found neither on the expanded MSC nor on sorted MSC.

The most frequent minimal regions with gains (with more than one consecutive clone gain) are shown in Table 2, and they are localized in 19p13.3, 11q13.1 and 20q13.33. Supplementary Table 1 of supplemental data shows the gains and losses in the different chromosomal regions. When unsupervised hierarchical cluster analysis of the array-CGH was performed, two major genetic subgroups emerged. Seven samples were grouped in Cluster I, and six samples in Cluster II (Figure 3).

Interestingly, five out of the six cases included in cluster II corresponded to 5q₋ syndrome patients (cases 21, 22, 24, 26 and 27). The other patient had been diagnosed as refractory anemia (RA) but when the diagnosis was revised FISH analysis revealed 4% of 5q₋ cells (case 1), and by morphology hypoplastic erythropoiesis and 8% of mononucleated megakaryocytes were observed.

By contrast, cluster I grouped cases other than 5q₋ syndromes except for one patient diagnosed as a refractory anemia with excess of blasts type 1 (RAEB-1) but with 5q deletion (case 12).

Significance analysis of microarrays indicated that the differences between these two clusters occurred just in 26 bacterial artificial chromosome (BAC). When looking at these clones and taking into account only regions with at least two consecutive clones affected, chromosomal regions 11q13, 17q25, 19q13, 20q13 and 22q13.2 were gained in 100 or 80% of the cases in cluster II; by contrast a normal copy or deletion status was observed in cluster I (Supplementary Table 2).

To confirm the gains of these regions a FISH analysis was performed using the DNA probes from 1q31.12 (RPC111-440G22). As it can be observed in Figure 3, the gains in chromosome 1q31 in MSC were confirmed. It should be pointed out that the concomitant analysis of array-CGH on HC from three cases and T lymphocytes from other four cases allowed us to show that the alterations of MSC were not present either on HC or on T cells and also showing that these alterations are not constitutional. Supplementary Figure 5 shows an example.

When sorted MSCs were analyzed also some genomic changes could be observed, the following regions being the most frequent gains observed among the cases: 1q31, 10q26 and 20q13. It is mandatory to point out that the purity of the sorted MSC was above 99% (Figure 1). To confirm these genomic gains a FISH analysis was performed using the DNA probe from the 7p13 BAC that showed a very high genomic gain at this level in case number 34. The expanded MSCs from the same patient were analyzed. As shown in Supplementary Figure 6 several signals can be observed confirming the genomic gain.

Discussion

The interactions between the malignant clone and the BM microenvironment have recently emerged as an important player in cancer development.²⁹ However, little is known about the characteristics of the BM stroma cells from cancer patients.

In this study we have observed that in MDS patients, the MSC, the progenitors of BM stromal cells display an abnormal phenotype, function and genetic features.

The development of MDS is a complex process and a multistep model has been proposed.^{1,3,30,31} In this model an abnormal hematopoietic clone would interact with an altered BM microenvironment. Newer knowledge is appearing showing new molecular alterations involved in MDS development, recently it has been shown that ribosomal proteins could participate in some MDSs development such as 5q-syndrome.³² Although there is intensive research on the role of stromal cells in the pathophysiology of inefficient hematopoiesis,^{6,8,33,34} a consensus has not been reached. As the stroma is a network of different cell types and molecules we decided to focus on MSC to have a homogeneous cell population devoid of HC. With our selection method the purity of MSC was above 98% in all cases.

The growth kinetics of MSC from MDS patients has been controversial with some authors showing an impaired expansion potential^{4,8} and others obtaining a growth pattern similar to those of normal BM.⁷ Our results support the former data with a lower expansion capacity of MSC from MDS patients. The differences with other reports may be because of the great variability observed among MSC growth in MDS or because cases with absence of growth were not included in the analysis.

Regarding MSC immunophenotype, the expression of CD90 has been previously reported to be lower in MSC from MDS.^{8,10} In our series this feature was also observed but differences did not reach statistical significance. By contrast MDS-derived MSC showed a significant lower expression of two adhesion molecules (CD 104 and CD 105); this lower expression could be involved in the altered relationship between BM stroma and HC. The intensity of CD 105 is not always analyzed and it has just been found to be lower

in one study¹⁰ and CD 104 has not been previously analyzed.

To gain insight on the mechanisms involved in the lower expansion capacity, cell cycle and apoptosis analysis were performed. No differences between MDS and controls, in the cell cycle distribution were observed and although apoptosis was slightly higher in MDS patients the small differences do not justify the cell growth impairment present in this disorder. Accordingly further studies are needed to explain the low expansion capacity of MDS.

Regarding cytogenetic abnormalities, Soenen-Cornu et al.⁷ have shown that MSC from MDS patients do not harbor the same cytogenetic abnormalities present on their HC counterpart. Nevertheless, other groups have reported the existence of chromosomal aberrations in MSC from MDS.^{8,9} To gain more insight in this field we have conducted array-CGH studies, which allow to study a greater number of genes than conventional cytogenetic or FISH, and in all cases some abnormalities were observed but when control's MSCs were analyzed they did not display similar changes. In addition the chromosomal imbalances present in the MSC were different than the ones observed in the HC. To confirm that these genomic changes were present in MSCs, a FISH analysis using the same probes than those used in array-CGH were done and the genomic gains were confirmed (Figure 4).

It should be stressed that genomic gains were much more frequent than losses which were observed in only four cases. The chromosomal regions mostly affected are shown in Table 2. Interestingly, these gained regions contained important genes involved on cell-cell adhesion process (such as R-Cadherin) or tumor development (kallikreins).

With these findings it could be argued that changes can be rather unspecific and because of changes associated with the cell expansion process. To analyze whether non-expanded MSCs could have genomic changes a sorting process was performed. It is well known that MSCs have no specific markers^{14,15} but it has been recently published that a bright expression for CD73 and CD271 markers allows to enrich in MSCs 21 cells obtained by this method (CD45₊, CD34₊, CD73 and CD 271 bright) also showed genomic changes and once again gains were more frequent than losses. These genomic changes were also confirmed by performing FISH studies using the same probes but in the expanded MSCs from the same patient (Supplementary Figure 6). These data confirm the presence of genomic changes in MSCs from MDS patients and that the same changes are also present after they were cultured. However, it cannot be excluded that the expansion process could increase the genomic changes observed in expanded population. An interesting observation of the present study was the finding that MSC from different MDS patients clustered into two clearly separated branches when an unsupervised analysis was performed. In cluster II the MSC from all patients with 5q₋ syndrome were grouped together with the MSC from another patient that, curiously, was not diagnosed as having 5q₋ syndrome because only a low proportion of cells (4%) showed this alteration by FISH but on morphological ground it was similar to 5q₋ syndrome patients (hypoplastic erythropoiesis and hypolobulated megakaryocytes in a patient with anemia and a normal platelet count). These features suggest that BM stroma and/or their MSC precursors are involved in the pathophysiology of MDS. Moreover, our data revealed in the 5q₋ syndrome samples the existence of a singular genomic profile, including the overexpression of some genomic regions (7p22.3, 19p13.3, 19p13.11), which could play an important role in the pathogenesis and disease characteristics. It has been recently proposed that the most likely model for MDS could be a dual pathogenesis including hematopoietic stem cells abnormalities and an abnormal BM 'milieu'. In the 5q₋ syndrome the defective erythropoiesis is secondary to a defect in ribosomal protein function but this abnormality does not explain the growth advantage of hematopoietic stem cells suggesting that other abnormalities could be involved in the pathogenesis of this MDS subtype.³⁵ It must be stressed that the 5q₋ syndrome represents a very well defined MDS subtype and has been recently accepted as a distinct entity by the WHO classification with clearly distinct clinical and prognostic features that differ from those of the other MDS.

The role of the microenvironment in the tumor development was originally proposed by Paget in his 'seed and soil' hypothesis.³⁶ Recent reports have shown that some genetic changes occur in the stroma during the earliest stages of human carcinogenesis.³⁷ This genetically unstable stroma may facilitate the growth of malignant clonal cells^{38,39} leading to a 'permissive milieu'. The microenvironment in MDS has been proposed to play a key role in the MDS development and new treatment strategies are being developed for these targets.^{2,40,41} Our results illustrate that MSC from MDS display not only distinct phenotypic and

growth characteristics but also singular genomic changes, some of them specially associated with particular MDS subtypes.

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References

- 1 Catenacci DV, Schiller GJ. Myelodysplastic syndromes: a comprehensive review. *Blood Rev* 2005; 19: 301–319.
- 2 List AF, Vardiman J, Issa JP, DeWitte TM. Myelodysplastic syndromes. *Hematol Am Soc Hematol Educ Program* 2004, 297–317.
- 3 Fenaux P. Myelodysplastic syndromes: From pathogenesis and prognosis to treatment. *Semin Hematol* 2004; 41: 6–12.
- 4 Tauro S, Hepburn MD, Bowen DT, Pippard MJ. Assessment of stromal function, and its potential contribution to deregulation of hematopoiesis in the myelodysplastic syndromes. *Haematologica* 2001; 86: 1038–1045.
- 5 Flores-Figueroa E, Gutierrez-Espindola G, Montesinos JJ, rana-Trejo RM, Mayani H. In vitro characterization of hematopoietic microenvironment cells from patients with myelodysplastic syndrome. *Leuk Res* 2002; 26: 677–686.
- 6 Deeg HJ. Marrow stroma in MDS: culprit or bystander? *Leuk Res* 2002; 26: 687–688.
- 7 Soenen-Cornu V, Tourino C, Bonnet ML, Guillier M, Flamant S, Kotb R et al. Mesenchymal cells generated from patients with myelodysplastic syndromes are devoid of chromosomal clonal markers and support short- and long-term hematopoiesis in vitro. *Oncogene* 2005; 24: 2441–2448.
- 8 Flores-Figueroa E, rana-Trejo RM, Gutierrez-Espindola G, Perez-Cabrera A, Mayani H. Mesenchymal stem cells in myelodysplastic syndromes: phenotypic and cytogenetic characterization. *Leuk Res* 2005; 29: 215–224.
- 9 Blau O, Hofmann WK, Baldus CD, Thiel G, Serbent V, Schumann E et al. Chromosomal aberrations in bone marrow mesenchymal stroma cells from patients with myelodysplastic syndrome and acute myeloblastic leukemia. *Exp Hematol* 2007; 35: 221–229.
- 10 Campioni D, Moretti S, Ferrari L, Punturieri M, Castodi GL, Lanza F. Immunophenotypic heterogeneity of bone marrow-derived mesenchymal stromal cells from patients with hematologic disorders: correlation with bone marrow microenvironment. *Haematologica* 2006; 91: 364–368.
- 11 Ramakrishnan A, Awaya N, Bryant E, Torok-Storb B. The stromal component of the marrow microenvironment is not derived from the malignant clone in MDS. *Blood* 2006; 108: 772–773.
- 12 Vardiman JW, Harris NL, Brunning RD. The World Health Organization (WHO) classification of the myeloid neoplasms. *Blood* 2002; 100: 2292–2302.
- 13 Minguell JJ, Erices A, Conget P. Mesenchymal stem cells. *Exp Biol Med (Maywood)* 2001; 226: 507–520.
- 14 Villaron EM, Almeida J, Lopez-Holgado N, Alcoceba M, Sanchez- barca LI, Sanchez-Guijo FM et al. Mesenchymal stem cells are present in peripheral blood and can engraft after allogeneic hematopoietic stem cell transplantation. *Haematologica* 2004; 89:1421–1427.
- 15 Dominici M, Le Blanc K, Mueller I, Slapar-Cortenbach I, Marini F, Krause D et al. Minimal criteria for defining multipotent mesenchymal stromal cells. The International Society for Cellular Therapy position statement. *Cytotherapy* 2006; 8: 315–317.
- 16 del Canizo MC, Fernandez ME, Lopez A, Vidriales B, Villaron E, Arroyo JL et al. Immunophenotypic analysis of myelodysplastic syndromes. *Haematologica* 2003; 88: 402–407.
- 17 Pittenger MF, Mackay AM, Beck SC, Jaiswal RK, Douglas R, Mosca JD et al. Multilineage potential of adult human mesenchymal stem cells. *Science* 1999; 284: 143–147.

- 18 Conget PA, Minguell JJ. Phenotypical and functional properties of human bone marrow mesenchymal progenitor cells. *J Cell Physiol* 1999; 181: 67–73.
- 19 Blanco B, Perez-Simon JA, Sanchez-Abarca LI, Carvajal-Vergara X, Mateos J, Vidriales B et al. Bortezomib induces selective depletion of alloreactive T lymphocytes and decreases the production of Th1 cytokines. *Blood* 2006; 107: 3575–3583.
- 20 Garcia-Montero AC, Jara-Acevedo M, Teodosio C, Sanchez ML, Nunez R, Prados A et al. KIT mutation in mast cells and other bone marrow hematopoietic cell lineages in systemic mast cell disorders: a prospective study of the Spanish Network on Mastocytosis (REMA) in a series of 113 patients. *Blood* 2006; 108: 2366–2372.
- 21 Buhring HJ, Battula VL, Tremel S, Schewe B, Kanz L, Vogel W. Novel markers for the prospective isolation of human MSC. *Ann N Y Acad Sci* 2007; 1106: 262–271.
- 22 Carter NP, Fiegler H, Piper J. Comparative analysis of comparative genomic hybridization microarray technologies: report of a workshop sponsored by the Wellcome Trust. *Cytometry* 2002; 49: 43–48.
- 23 Fiegler H, Carr P, Douglas EJ, Burford DC, Hunt S, Scott CE et al. DNA microarrays for comparative genomic hybridization based on DOP-PCR amplification of BAC and PAC clones. *Genes Chromosomes Cancer* 2003; 36: 361–374.
- 24 Herrero J, Al-Shahrour F, az-Uriarte R, Mateos A, Vaquerizas JM, Santoyo J et al. GEPAS: A web-based resource for microarray gene expression data analysis. *Nucleic Acids Res* 2003; 31: 3461–3467.
- 25 Eisen MB, Spellman PT, Brown PO, Botstein D. Cluster analysis and display of genome-wide expression patterns. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 1998; 95: 14863–14868.
- 26 Tusher VG, Tibshirani R, Chu G. Significance analysis of microarrays applied to the ionizing radiation response. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 2001; 98: 5116–5121.
- 27 Gonzalez MB, Hernandez JM, Garcia JL, Lumbreras E, Castellanos M, Hernandez JM et al. The value of fluorescence in situ hybridization for the detection of 11q in multiple myeloma. *Haematologica* 2004; 89: 1213–1218.
- 28 Perez-Simon JA, Caballero D, Diez-Campelo M, Lopez-Pérez R, Mateos G, Canizo C et al. Chimerism and minimal residual disease monitoring after reduced intensity conditioning (RIC) allogeneic transplantation. *Leukemia* 2002; 16: 1423–1431.
- 29 Li H, Fan X, Houghton J. Tumor microenvironment: the role of the tumor stroma in cancer. *J Cell Biochem* 2007; 101: 805–815.
- 30 Hellstrom-Lindberg E, Willman C, Barrett AJ, Sauntharajah Y. Achievements in understanding and treatment of myelodysplastic syndromes. *Hematol Am Soc Hematol Educ Program* 2000, 110–132.
- 31 Mufti GJ. Pathobiology, classification, and diagnosis of myelodysplastic syndrome. *Best Pract Res Clin Haematol* 2004; 17: 543–557.
- 32 Ebert BL, Pretz J, Bosco J, Chang CY, Tamayo P, Galili N et al. Identification of RPS14 as a 5q- syndrome gene by RNA interference screen. *Nature* 2008; 451: 335–339.
- 33 List AF. New approaches to the treatment of myelodysplasia. *Oncologist* 2002; 7 (Suppl 1): 39–49.
- 34 Corey SJ, Minden MD, Barber DL, Kantarjian H, Wang JC, Schimmer AD. Myelodysplastic syndromes: the complexity of stem-cell diseases. *Nat Rev Cancer* 2007; 7: 118–129.
- 35 Cazzola M. Myelodysplastic syndrome with isolated 5q deletion (5q- syndrome). A clonal stem cell disorder characterized by defective ribosome biogenesis. *Haematologica* 2008; 93:967–972.
- 36 Albin A, Sporn MB. The tumour microenvironment as a target for chemoprevention. *Nat Rev Cancer* 2007; 7: 139–147.
- 37 Ishiguro K, Yoshida T, Yagishita H, Numata Y, Okayasu T. Epithelial and stromal genetic instability contributes to genesis of colorectal adenomas. *Gut* 2006; 55: 695–702.
- 38 Mueller MM, Fusenig NE. Friends or foes? Bipolar effects of the tumour stroma in cancer. *Nat Rev Cancer* 2004; 4: 839–849.
- 39 Hideshima T, Mitsiades C, Tonon G, Richardson PG, Anderson KC. Understanding multiple myeloma pathogenesis in the bone marrow to identify new therapeutic targets. *Nat Rev Cancer* 2007; 7: 585–598.
- 40 Giagounidis AA, Haase S, Heinsch M, Gohring G, Schlegelberg B, Aul C. Lenalidomide in the context of complex karyotype or interrupted treatment: case reviews of del(5q)MDS patients with unexpected responses. *Ann Hematol* 2007; 86: 133–137.

41 Mufti G, List AF, Gore SD, Ho AY. Myelodysplastic syndrome. Hematol Am Soc Hematol Educ Program 2003, 176–199.

Table 1 Clinical and cytogenetic characteristics of MDS patients

Case number	Diagnosis WHO	Age	Sex	Conventional cytogenetic analysis	Informative markers by FISH
1	RA	60	F	No mitosis	5q- (4%)
2	RA	72	M	46, XY [20]	No marker
3	RA	64	F	46, XX [4]	Not done
4	RARS	40	F	46, XX,t(6;11)(q22; q14) [16]	Not done
5	RARS	81	M	46, XY [4] 45, X,-Y [16]	Not done
6	RARS	68	F	46, XX [20]	No marker
7	RARS	68	F	46, XX [20]	No marker
8	RARS	72	M	46, XY [3] 46, XY,-Y,+8 [17]	+ 8 (51%)
9	RARS	77	M	No mitosis	7q- (8%)
10	RCMD-RS	80	M	No mitosis	No marker
11	RAEB-1	55	F	46, XX [10] 46, XX, del (5)(q13q31)[8]	5q- (56%)
12	RAEB-1	87	F	No mitosis	5q- (48%)
13	RAEB-1	77	M	46, XY [20]	No marker
14	RAEB-1	62	M	46, XY [20]	No marker
15	RAEB-2	55	M	46, XY [21]	Not done
16	RAEB-2	72	M	46, XY [20]	No marker
17	RAEB-2	89	F	46, XX [20]	Not done
18	RAEB-2	79	M	46, XY [11] 47, XY,+8 [6] 46, XY, del(9)(q31) [2]	+ 8 (13%)
19	RAEB-2	40	F	46, XX [20]	No marker
20	RAEB-2	70	M	46, XY [12] 47, XY,+8 [8]	+ 8 (55%)
21	5q- syndrome	52	M	46, XY [5] 46, XY, del(5)(q13q31) [17]	5q- (41%)
22	5q- syndrome	79	F	5q 46, XX [6] 46, XX, del(5)(q13q31) [14]	5q- (46%)
23	5q- syndrome	34	F	No mitosis	5q- (20%)
24	5q- syndrome	62	F	46, XX [3] 46, XX, del (5) (q14q34) [16]	5q- (27%)
25	5q- syndrome	62	M	53, XX, +1, +2, +11, +11, +14, +21, +22 [6] 46, XY [5] 46, XY, del(5)(q13q31) [15]	-5q- (66%)
26	5q- syndrome	63	F	46, XX [6] 46, XX, del(5)(q13q31) [14]	5q- (49%)
27	5q- syndrome	75	M	No mitosis	5q- (40%)
28	Unclassifiable	34	F	No mitosis	No marker
29	Unclassifiable	69	M	46, XY [12] 47, XY,+8 [8]	+ 8 (55%)
30	Unclassifiable	79	M	46, XY [20]	Not done
31	Unclassifiable	62	F	46, XX [20]	No marker
32	Unclassifiable	83	M	No mitosis	No marker
33	RARS	71	M	46, XY [6] 46, XY,+8 [14]	Not done
34	5q- syndrome	81	F	No mitosis	5q- (48%)
35	5q- syndrome	48	M	No mitosis	5q- (37%)
36	5q- syndrome	73	M	46, XY [5] 46, XY, del(5)(q13q31) [15]	Not done

RA: refractory anemia; RARS: refractory anemia with ringed sideroblasts; RCMD-RS: refractory cytopenia with multilineage dysplasia and ringed sideroblasts; RAEB-1: refractory anemia with excess blasts 1; RAEB-2: refractory anemia with ringed sideroblasts 2; Myelodysplastic syndrome, unclassifiable, 5q- syndrome. Not markers: normal FISH for 5q, 7q and 8.

Table 2 Commonly gained regions of copy number changes identified in MSC of patients with MDS assessed by array-CGH

Clones name (start-end)	Locus	Frequency (%)
RP11-268O21-CTC-482H14	19p13.3	38
RP11-424 ^o 11-RP11-147G6	11q13.1	31
RP5-1107C24-RP4-563E14	20q13.33	31
RP11-440G22-RP11-142L4	1q31.2	23
RP11-12A13-RP11-12J13	3q11.2	23
RP11-11N6-RP11-9B6	4q22.1	23
RP11-510K8-RP4-607J2	7p22	23
RP4-560O14-RP11-575G1	7q21.11	23
RP11-478P5-RP11-196E5	17q25.1	23
CTD-3149D2-CTC-251H24	19p13.11	23
CTD-2545M3-RP11-10I11	19q13.33	23
RP11-113F1-RP11-351D2	21q22.3	23

Figure 1 Isolation of MSC from BM by sorting. Owing to the low proportion of CD45⁻/CD73⁺/CD34⁻/CD271⁺ cells in BM (a), a gate is performed in the CD73⁺/CD271⁺ region in which MSCs are located (b). Finally the purity of the population is analyzed (c) being > 99%. The MSC population is indicated in black, the contaminating cells in gray.

Figure 2 Morphological differences. Appearance of MSC from controls (a) under the inverted microscope ($\times 10$) and MDS-MSC (1b). In the MDS-MSC (b) layer the presence of thick and granular cells is evident (arrow).

Figure 3 Unsupervised cluster analysis of array-CGH from 13 MDS-MSC cases. Each column represents one case and each row represented one BAC clone. Cutoffs were calculated, and 1 was assigned for gains and 0 and -1 for no changes and losses, respectively. Losses are indicated in green and gains in red. The samples were clustered with the order of the BACs intact. The classification tree on top suggests two genetic subgroups.

Figure 4 Confirmation by FISH of the genomic alterations found by array-CGH. Case 26. FISH with the probe from RPC111-4440G22 on MSC, the three green signals confirm the gains in 1q31.12.